

EFFECTS OF EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND ON ATTITUDE TOWARDS WOMEN

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Abstract

The present research was conducted to identify if there is an association between education level and total AWS score. For this a shortened version of Attitude towards women Scale (AWS) developed by Janet T. Spence and Robert Helmreich in the early 1970s were used. Present paper focuses on the attitude towards women among H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College. The objectives are to study and compare the attitude towards women among H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College. The findings of the study revealed that there is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Graduates students and Graduates & Post Graduate students. Whereas mean scores of the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College differs significantly.

Key words: Attitudes toward Women Scale, South Mumbai, Students, Educational Background, AWS, attitude

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Introduction

India is mainly dominated by patriarchal society, where male member of the family dominates. The women are still facing hardship in getting educated, selecting their career and going for job. Many parents are allowing their girl child to get the education in urban areas. But very apprehensive in sending the girl to work. In India status of women has been a subject of debate and discussion. From birth, the girl child considered as burden of the family due to many social customs prevailed in India. One such custom is Dowry. Due to this woman in this country are not receiving the same opportunities of education, medical attention, respect and dignity from the family members.

Jain; Agarwal; Billaiya; Devi (2017). In their research study point out that the illiterate mother of a girl child itself a victim of neglect, doesn't support the girl for their education Rout; Lewis; Kagan (1999) conducted a study in 1999 in which the authors compared data collected from working women in India with working women in west The results showed that Major work-family pressures are almost similar for women in both groups for the reasons like overload, time pressures, constant fatigue, work interfering with relations & with children and guilt and anxiety over children while at work.

Attitude towards women scale was used differently by different researchers. Öngen, (2006), examined the effects of

gender, academic domain and grade level on attitudes towards women in Turkish university students. The author used short version of the AWS. ANOVA results applied on total scores revealed significant effect of gender on attitude towards women. Females reported more liberal views about women as compared to male. Whatley (2008) investigated the factor structure of the shorter version of AWS and the study with undergraduate shows that AWS is measuring a unitary attitude towards women. Many researchers used the scale along with other tools to explore the link of attitude towards women with other variables (Parks & Mary, 2004; Lizotte. 2018)

Purpose of the Study

The Attitudes toward Women Scale (AWS), developed by Janet T. Spence and Robert Helmreich in the early 1970s. This scale measures attitudes about the rights and roles of women - relative to men - in occupational, educational and relational domains. There are two version for this scale one with 25 items and another with 15 items. The AWS originally wanted to assess the behavioral patterns which seems to appropriate for men and women in society. In those times it believed that men will work for the family, support the family financially whereas the women in the family will cook, take care of kids and do household works. The researchers in this research selected the shortened version of the scale. The researchers wanted to explore whether the educational level of the college students have any association with the total score of attitudes towards women scale.

Thus, the present paper is an attempt to highlight how students with varied academic level and its effect on attitude towards women score. The researchers has selected the problem due to its relevance and need in today's learning environment. The researchers has attempted to find out the attitude towards women among H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives formulated by researchers for the present study.

1. To study the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College.
2. To ascertain the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Graduates students of South Mumbai College.
3. To ascertain the level of attitude towards women among Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College.
4. To compare the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Graduates students of South Mumbai College.
2. There is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards women among Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College.
3. There is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College.

Scope of the Study

The study mainly focuses on the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College. It includes only students of South Mumbai College. The study is restricted only to female students.

Delimitations of the Study

The study is restricted to students of South Mumbai College only. Only college students are included in the study. The study is limited to students of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College. The study does not include students from other professional or technical colleges.

Research Design

The method adopted for a study depends upon the nature and purpose of the study. The present research surveys the attitude towards women among H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College. The sample comprised of only college students of South Mumbai. The sample comprised of 98 female college students. For the present study, the researcher has used the Descriptive method of the quantitative type.

Table 1 Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of attitude towards women

Category	Low (%)	Moderate (%)	High (%)
H.S.C.	18	70	12
Graduate	14	71	15
Post Graduate	13	73	14
Overall	19	66	15

Fig. 1 Showing Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of attitude towards women

From table 1 and Figure 1,

- 13% of Post Graduate students & 18% of H.S.C. students have low level of attitude towards women. Whereas 12% of H.S.C. students 15% of Graduate students have high level of attitude towards women. Also 71% of Graduate students & 73% of Post Graduate students have moderate level of attitude towards women. The high score of AWS is associated with the progressive thinking of students towards the rights of women
- In the overall category of Boards, 19% of students have low level of attitude towards women. Whereas 15% students have high level of attitude towards women. Also 66% of students have moderate level of attitude towards women.

Testing the Hypotheses - In the present study, each hypothesis was tested by using the t – test.

Table 2 Relevant statistics of mean scores of the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College

Hy.	Groups	N	df	Mean	SD	SE _d	t (cal)	t(tab)	L. of Sig.
1	H.S.C.	33	66	27.12	6.45	1.51	1.22	1.98	NS
	Graduate	35		25.29	5.97				
2	Graduate	35	63	25.29	5.97	1.41	0.87	1.98	NS
	Post Graduate	30		24.07	5.36				
3	H.S.C.	33	61	27.12	6.45	1.49	2.05	1.98	S
	Post Graduate	30		24.07	5.36				

- From the preceding table for hypothesis 1, it is evident that the calculated t-value is 1.22, which is significant at 0.05 level with df = 66. It reflects that mean scores of the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Graduate students of South Mumbai College do not differ significantly. The null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Graduates students of South Mumbai College is accepted.
- From the preceding table for hypothesis 2, it is evident that the calculated t-value is 0.87, which is significant at 0.05 level with df = 63. It reflects that mean scores of the level of attitude towards women among Graduate & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College does not differ significantly. The null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards women among Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College is accepted.
- From the preceding table for hypothesis 3, it is evident that the calculated t-value is 2.05, which is significant at 0.05 level with df = 61. It reflects that mean scores of the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College differ significantly. The null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College are rejected. Further the mean score of level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. students is 27.12 which is significantly higher than that of Post Graduate students whose mean score is 24.07. It may therefore be said that H.S.C. students were found to possess a significantly high level of attitude towards women as compared to Postgraduate students of South Mumbai College.

Major findings

1. There is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Graduates of South Mumbai College is accepted.
2. There is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards women among Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College is accepted.
3. There is no significant difference in the level of attitude towards women among H.S.C. & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College is rejected.

Conclusion:

From the findings it may be concluded that between H.S.C. & Graduates students and between Graduates & Post Graduates students have the same level of attitude towards women.

Further between H.S.C. & Post Graduate students have different level of attitude towards women.

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